

Reading Comprehension: A Strategy for Enhancing Academic Performance

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Abstract:

Reading skill is a complex one, especially when it comes to reading comprehension. It requires special training, which is not provided by teachers in the class. Teachers focus on decoding and developing vocabulary. ESL students face more difficulties at higher levels as they are not able to comprehend unseen passages. Many researchers have proven that if teachers train students with various strategies related to reading comprehension, it will be helpful for the students to comprehend any reading material.

Keywords: Reading comprehension, Reading comprehension strategies

Introduction:

English is considered a second language in many countries. In India, it is considered a window language and a link language. In India, it is used as a second language. Language development includes listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills. In that reading skill is very complex. Basic reading can be developed by various activities if teachers allocate proper time for it in class, but when it comes to developing reading comprehension, teachers do not train students for it. They focus on decoding words and vocabulary. For developing reading comprehension, they either translate or paraphrase the text. The students of ESL face more difficulty, and if they are not trained at the school level, they face difficulties at higher levels.

Review of Related Literature:

According to the ANNUAL STATUS OF EDUCATION REPORT (2017), 53% of all 14-year-olds in the sample can read English sentences. For 18-year-old youth, this figure is closer to 60%, and of those who can read English sentences, 79% can understand the meaning of the sentences. Even among youth in this age group who have completed eight years of schooling, a significant proportion still lack foundational skills like reading.

As per the research study conducted by Shobha Sinha (2012) in India, primary-level instruction focuses on decoding words, and at higher grades, it focuses on developing vocabulary. For comprehension, teachers translate the passage.

The study conducted by Narasimhan (2004) on the children of elite schools in Mumbai assessed their comprehension of narrative, expository, and instructional texts. The students displayed a wide range of proficiency in their performance and performed lower than the average in the public exams. Narasimhan explained that this result showed that the students did not have the competence to comprehend unfamiliar texts.

The study conducted by Dolores Durkin (1978) in "What classroom observations reveal about reading comprehension instruction" also concluded that teachers give very little time for reading and comprehension during instruction, whereas it is a

more important skill to be developed among students.

Review of literature also proved that teachers do not train students for reading comprehension but assess the same. If teachers train the students in reading strategies, it will help to comprehend the text in an effective manner.

Strategies for Reading Comprehension:

These are a few reading strategies for students to develop reading comprehension.

Evaluating Text Structure:

There are different types of text structures, and many students are not aware of them. Students reading a wide variety of text types are not able to identify the type of text as they are unaware of the characteristics of various types of writing. Students need to be explicitly taught text structure and its characteristics of various text types. It has been found that students who are aware of text structure can highly relate to reading comprehension. Explicit teaching about text structure specific to the text type will help students to distinguish among several organizational patterns and help them find important information in texts in a more systematic and organized way. Once students can recognize the text structure, it enhances the student's ability to comprehend and recall the information read. Teachers should explain the knowledge of specific text type, organization, signal words, and questions to be asked about the text will help the students to know the text and comprehend it. When students first look at a text and skim through it or preview, they pick up some ideas about the layout and features of the text. This will help students to predict what the text will be about and work with the text background knowledge to help make predictions. Good readers make predictions and then check their predictions as they read.

There are different types of text such as description, sequence, cause and effect, compare, position statement and reason, and problem and solution. When teachers introduce these types of texts, students get confused with the basic structure of the text and cannot see the big picture. Teachers must explain each one with proper examples and

practice it in the daily classroom. Once the student understands the text structure, it helps them to comprehend the text.

Generating Questions:

Students, while reading, lose their concentration, and they keep on reading without understanding. If they are taught to generate questions as they read, it helps the students to comprehend. Skilled readers keep track of whether the author is making sense by asking themselves questions. If students pose and answer questions that clarify meaning and promote a deeper understanding of the text. Teachers should train the students to generate three types of questions. First type is 'Right there'. This question is about the factual knowledge which is in the text and the answer can be given in one word, a phrase, or one sentence. The second type of questions is 'Putting it together'. These questions can be answered by looking in the text in one or more sentences. To find out the answer, you must look in more than one place in the text and put the information together. The third type of questions is 'Think it out-Making connections' questions. These types of questions require thinking about what you have read, what you already know, and how it fits together. To enhance comprehension, questions can be asked not only by the reader but also by a peer or the teacher. Teachers often ask questions to see whether students understand what they have read. Understanding the different types of questions makes it easier to find the answers. Some questions require students to find facts about what they read, while others require students to draw conclusions or make inferences.

Teaching students to generate their questions about a text helps with their understanding and assists them to answer questions set by others. Question generation includes previewing the text and then generating questions at three levels, Questions asked to help students get the facts rarely help students to construct an understanding of an author's message. They find answers but miss the important questions, the questions they should pose to themselves to guide their reading and understanding. Questions can be generated at any time during the reading process that is before, during, and after reading.

Fix-up Strategies:

To fix up the strategy which suits students, they should be trained for self-monitoring. Students who know how to self-monitor can make self-corrections and retain information from what they have read. Self-monitoring involves 'metacognitive awareness,' which is 'knowing when what one is reading makes sense by monitoring and controlling one's comprehension. Self-monitoring is an important metacognitive skill for improving reading comprehension. It can be taught by developing the student's internal dialogue or self-talk. Active

readers, as they read, monitor how well they understand what they are reading. When reading difficult material, these students engage in self-monitoring strategies such as rereading portions of the text or reading slowly and trying to figure out the meaning of unfamiliar words important to understand it. Even realizing that repeated readings of a passage will make it significantly easier to recall its important content can be of benefit to many students. When students self-monitor, they need to be aware of when meaning breaks down, what they do not understand (word, sentence, paragraph), and make use of appropriate strategies to "fix-up." Students should visualize what is wrong or missing, keep the logical sequence in the text. Through self-talk try to understand what is wrong and incomplete, unclear in the meaning. Students should understand that reading must make sense, and when it does not, we need to do something to improve meaning, ask questions, reread, and read more slowly. When the text is not understood, find out the reason, understand text type features and prior knowledge of background, create an image in the mind, make connections and sometimes ask for help. Teachers should teach all these strategies to students so they can make use of these strategies as per their requirement.

Main Idea:

Once the students understand the main idea of the text, it will be easy for them to comprehend the text. Students should determine the main idea it helps the readers to recall important information. Locating the main idea and significant details help the reader understand the points the writer is attempting to express. Identifying the relationship between the main idea and significant details will improve comprehension. Students tell who and what the paragraph is about and what is important information about, teachers ask students to read the passage and find out who is doing what, underline the main sentences, find the main idea by finding initial sentences of the topic embedded within the paragraph, teachers develop the background knowledge, underline the main idea and circle supporting details, record the topic sentence and significant details using a graphic organizer, make use of background knowledge, contents, headings, and subheadings to find out the main idea.

Visualizing:

Visualizing is sometimes called sensory imaging, creating pictures in your mind like a 'movie in your mind'. Visualizing is a very good strategy when it comes to abstract ideas. Students can visualize the content by using prior knowledge and experiences to create a mental image from what is happening in a text. Sometimes it is helpful for students to close their eyes and imagine what is being read to them. Visualizing brings the text to life, engages the imagination, and uses all of the

senses. Visualization cannot be developed in one day; teachers must train students from their daily life and day-to-day activity, gradually taking students from concrete to abstract thinking. Read simple and short stories and ask students to imagine and then gradually take difficult texts.

Conclusion:

Reading comprehension is essential for secondary and higher secondary students not only from an academic viewpoint but for the future as well. If students are not trained with reading comprehension strategies, it will be difficult for them to comprehend unknown texts. In Indian classroom teacher assess the students for comprehension but take less efforts them for the same. As per New Education policy 2020 education should develop higher order thinking, critical thinking among student for that student should read lot of reference material, understand it, and make use of it for that these reading strategies will be useful specially for ESL users.

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